

Arulin Hausa: Bitar Illa A Cikin Wasu Baitocin Waƙoƙi

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Tsakure

Aruli wani fannin ilmi ne da ake amfani da shi domin nazarin waƙa, musamman rubutacciya. Kamar kowane fanni na ilmi, shi ma aruli yana da ka'idoji da kalmomi na fannu waɗanda suka kebanta da shi. Wannan takarda za ta yi koƙarin duba ne kan wasu baitoci na waƙoƙin Hausa da ake samun illa a cikinsu da kuma fito da bayanin nau'inta. Haka kuma za a waiwaiya game da ma'anar aruli da gaba da kafafuwa da kuma karuruwan da aruli ya kunsu a takaice. Sannan za a yi bayani dangane da yadda ake samun illa, ko sakiya kamar yadda waɗansu masana suka kira ta. Duba da yadda take afkuwa a cikin waƙa, ta hanyar kafa madoga da wasu daga cikin waƙoƙi. Kazalika, takardar za ta bibiyi nau'o'in illa da kuma nau'in naƙasun da ke shiga a cikin kowace gaba da ke cikin kafa.

Gabatarwa

“Arul” kalma ce ta Larabci, ana rubuta ta kamar haka “ARUD”. Lokacin da Hausawa suka aro wannan ilmi daga Larabci, sai suka aro shi tare da kalmar, amma sai suka yi mata kwaskwarima don furta ta ya dace da lafazin Hausa. Domin samun haka, sai aka sauya baƙin “D” ya koma “L” kuma aka fara wasalin ‘i’ a ƙarshen kalmar don daɗin furuci ga Bahausha, sai kalmar ta koma “ARULI”. (Dunfawa, 2002 da Bello, 2014, Tilde, 2016 da Muhammad, 2019).

Masana da manazarta sun yi sabani dangane da ma'anar da larabawa suka ba wannan kalma ta fuskar harshe. Wasu suna ganin kalmar tana nufin wata hanya mai wuyar bi, wasu kuma suna ganin tana nufin garin Makka. Ta fuskar manazarta kuwa, kalmar aruli na nufin wani ilmi ne na sanin kimiyyar waƙa, kamar karinta da muryarta da amsa-amonta. (Dunfawa, 2002:1).

Aruli wani ilmi ne da ake amfani da shi wajen nazarin waƙa musamman rubutacciya. Yahya, (2002:1-2).

Amma a wajen Dunfawa, (2002:1), ya bayyana ma'anar Aruli da cewa “Aruli wani fannin ilmi ne da ake amfani da shi domin nazarin waƙa, musamman rubutacciya”.

Sai dai Bello, (2014:4), kamar yadda Suleiman, (2021:2) ya fassaro shi, cewa ya yi “Mawaƙi, yana mai da hankalinsa dungurungum, wajen nazarin fitattun siffofin karin waƙa ta yadda zai san dukkanin ma'aunanta”.

Shi kuwa Muhammad, (2019:74) na da ra'ayin “Aruli yana bayani ne game da karin waƙa, wato hawa da saukar muryar mawaƙi a yayin rera waƙarsa”.

Duk da haka, Suleiman (2021:2) na ganin “Aruli wata irin dabara ce, ta bayar da dama ga mai karanta waƙa ya fahimci irin sautin da zai iya rera waƙa da yake karantawa tamkar dai, shi ya wallafa waƙa”.

Idan aka dubi waɗannan bayanai da masana da manazarta da daliban ilmi suka bayar, a fara tuntubawa da cewa “Aruli hanyar nazari ce ta sanin kimiyyar waƙa musamman rubutacciya, ta hanyar duba tsarin sautin fitar kowace gaba da ke haifar da reruwar amon kowace kafa”.

Kazalika, ya kyautu ga mai nazarin illa a cikin aruli ya fara bayyana, hanyar farko ta kimiyyar aruli, domin wajibi ne sai da ita illar ma ke samuwa domin ta ita ce illar ke kamawa a cikin kafa. Wato dai a ambaci gaba ta yadda za a samar da tushen fitar da sakiyar ko illar.

Gaba A Kimiyar Aruli

Gaba na ɗaya daga cikin muhimman ɓangarori na nazarin kimiyyar aruli, domin ita ce “kanwar uwar gami” na aikin aruli domin kuwa sai da ita ne ake samar da kafafu da karuruwa, uwa-uba kuwa, a kan kanta ne ake gane illa ko sakiya a cikin waƙar da ake nazari. Don haka masana suka tofa albarkacin bakinsu kan ma’anar gaba, inda wasu irin su:

Dunfawa, (2002:5) cewa ya yi “Gaba tana nufin ɗaya daga cikin furuttan da suka haɗu, suka yi kalma, wato furuci wanda baƙi da wasali suka haifar.

A fagen Aruli kuwa, gaba ita ce furuci mafi ƙanƙanci da ake samu a cikin kafa. Shi kuwa Tilde (2016:xiii), ya bayyana gaba da “cikakken furuci da ke fitowa daga baƙi, shi ake ce wa gaba”.

Amma Suleiman, (2021:3) cewa ya yi “gaba wadda da Ingilishi ake kira (syllable) wata ƙwayar sauti ce ta baƙi da wasali mafi ƙanƙanta da ake iya furtawa”.

Kazalika, masana sun tafi bai ɗaya, wajen bayyana cewar “Gaba iri biyu ce, doguwa da gajera ko kuma buɗaɗɗiya da rufaffiya, wadda a cikin ilmin Aruli ake alamta su kamar haka: gajera ‘O ko V’, doguwa kuwa, kamar haka: ‘OO ko –’. Wato, **BW** a gajera da **BWW** da kuma **BWB** a doguwar gaba.

Don haka da waɗannan alamomi ne ake nunin gajerar gaba ko doguwar gaba a wajen fitar da kafafun Aruli. Haka kuma a kan gane doguwar gaba ta hanyar lura da tsarinta wato rufaffiya ce mai **BWB** ko kuma gajera ce wadda ke da **BW** da ake iya ƙara wani abu a cikinta.

Kafa A Cikin Aruli

Kamar yadda aka bayyana, kafa ita ce wani sauti da ake samu ta hanyar harhaɗa gaɓoɓi uku ko fiye. Akwai ire-iren kafafuwa da ake amfani da su a cikin aruli guda 10. Ga yadda suke:

Alamar kafa

S/N	KAFA	ALAMAR 0	ALAMAR V
		00	--
1.	Fa’uulun	<u>0 00</u> 00	<u>v</u> --
2.	Mafaa’iilun	<u>0 0000</u> 00	<u>v</u> ---
3.	Mafaa’alatun	<u>0 000</u> 0 00	<u>v</u> -vv-
4.	Faa’ilaatun	<u>00 0</u> 00 00	-v --
5.	Faa’ilun	00 <u>0 00</u>	- v -
6.	Mustaf’ilun	00 00 <u>0 00</u>	-- v -
7.	Faa’ilaatun	00 <u>0 00</u> 00	- v --
8.	Mutafaa’ilun	0 0 00 <u>0 00</u>	vv - <u>v</u> -
9.	Maf’uulaatu	00 00 <u>00 0</u>	--- v
10.	Mustaf’ilun	00 00 0	-- v -

Idan an dubi tsarin kowace kafa za a ga akwai layi a tsakanin wasu gaɓoɓi, waɗanda ke nuna turke ne a wurin. Kuma duk inda turke ya ke, da wuya ka ci karo da wata illa ta shiga gaɓar. (Dunfawa, 2002 da Suleiman, 2021).

Kari A Cikin Aruli

Abin da zai biyo ga mai koyon aruli bayan ya san gaba ya kuma san kafa, shi ne sanin kari. Kari shi ne, wani rauji ko kiɗan waƙa, wanda ke haifar da reruwarta. Abin nufi a nan shi ne muddin babu kari, to, kuwa abin da ake son a kira waƙa ba zai reru ba, ba zai kuma zamo waƙa ba. (Dunfawa, 2002:9).

Sunayen da masana suka ba waɗannan karuruwan su ne, kamar yadda suke goma sha shida a cikin larabci, ga su kamar haka:

Mutaƙaarab
Dawil
Hajaz
Wafir
Mutadaarak
Rajaz
Basit
Munsarih
Ramal
Madid
Hafif
Kamil
Muktalib
Mujtas
Sari'i
Mudari

(Dunfawa, 2002, da Tilde, 2014)

Nau'o'in Kari

Ta lura da yadda karuruwan aruli suke, watau guda goma sha shida a iya dubar su dangane da yadda ƙafafuwa ke haɗuwa su samar da su ya zuwa kaso uku, kamar haka:

Kafa ta maimaita kanta ta samar da kari:

A wannan nau'in ana samun karuruwa guda bakwai da kafa ko kafufu a daidaiƙun su kan samar da karin su ne kamar haka:

i. Waafir	3+3+3	Mafaa'alatun
ii. Kaamil	8+8+8	Mutafaa'ilun
iii. Hajaz	2+2+2	Mafaa'iilun
iv. Rajaz	6+6+6	Mustaf'ilun
v. Ramal	7+7+7	Faa'ilaatun
vi. Mutaƙaarab	1+1+1	Fa'uulun
vii. Mutadaarak	5+5+5	Faa'ilun

Kafa Gwamau ta samar da kari

A nan wata kafa na haɗuwa da wata kafa su samar da kari, watau a gwama wata da wata, a irin wannan ana samun kafafu guda takwas su ne:

i. Dawiil	1+2+1+2	Fa'uulun + Mafaa'iilun
ii. Madid	7+5+7+5	Faa'ilaatun + Faa'ilun
iii. Basit	6+5+6+5	Mustaf'ilun + Faa'ilun
iv. Munsari	6+9+6+9	Mustaf'ilun + Maf'uulaatu
v. Hafif	7+10+7+10	Faa'ilaatun + Mustaf'ilun
vi. Mudaarii'i	2+7+2+7	Mafaa'iilun + Faa'ilaatun
vii. Muktalib	9+6+9+6	Maf'uulaatu + Mustaf'ilun
viii. Mujtas	6+7+6+7	Mustaf'ilun + Faa'ilaatun

Maimaitau a tara da wata kafa

A wannan nau'i ana samun kafa ta maimaita kanta sannan ta haɗu da wata su samar da kari, dangane da cikin karuruwan aruli sha shida, kari ɗaya ne ke da irin wannan siga,

watau Sarii'i inda kafa ta shida 6+6+9 watau Mustaf'ilun + Mustaf'ilun + Maf'uulaatu = Sarii'i.

Illa / Sakiya A Cikin Aruli

Dunfawa, (2002:50) ya kira wannan bigiren da sakiya a maimakon illa, domin kamar yadda ya bayyana, kalmar illa a Hausance tana nuna aibin wani abu wanda yake samuwarsa ga wani abu yana kawo masa cikak. Duk da ayyukan da masana suka gabatar, hannu bai kai kan wani aiki ba, wadda ya fito da bayanin illa sosai, amma duk da haka, wanda ya zo ga hannun ya nuna akwai illa kashi biyu.

Illa /Sakiya ta Ragi A Cikin Aruli

Wannan irin nau'in illa, ita ce wadda idan ta shiga ga kafa sai ta rage wa wata gaba daga cikin gaɓoɓinta. Kuma gabar ta kan zamo ta karshe a cikin layin baiti. Ita kanta illar ta ragi kamar yadda Dunfawa, (2002 :50) ya kadafta, ita ma ta kasu gidaje da kamar haka : Hazfi, Kafafi, Kada'i, Batari da Kashfi.

Illa Mai Ragi ta Hazfi

Ita wanna nau'in illa ta kan shiga ne, a cikin kafar waƙa musamman doguwar gabar karshe, sai ta share ta, ta mayar da ita gaba biyu idan kafar mai gaba uku ce, haka ma in mai gaba huɗu ce ta koma uku, in mai gaba biyar ce ta koma huɗu. Ire- iren waɗannan kafafu da ke karewa da doguwar gaba a karshe guda tara ne, huɗu suna da turke a farko, wato kafafu 'yan asali, sannan uku daga ciki na da turke a tsakiya, sauran biyun kuwa suna da turke a karshe, kafafun su ne kamar haka :

Fa'uulun	v --	sai ta koma	v --
Mafaa'iilun	v ---	ta koma	v --
Mafaa'alatun	v - vv -	ta koma	v - vv
Faa'ilaatun	- v --	ta koma	- v-
Faa'ilun	- v -	ta koma	- v
Mustaf'ilun	-- v -	ta koma	-- v
Faa'ilaatun	- v --	ta koma	- v -
Mutafaa'ilun	v v - v -	ta koma	v v - v
Mustaf'ilun	-- v -	ta koma	-- v

Waɗannan su ne kafafu guda tara masu karewa da doguwar gaba a karshe su, wanda illa ko sakiya ta hazfi za ta iya shiga, kuma idan ta shiga, shafe doguwar gabar karshe take gaba ɗaya. Ga misalan a cikin baitin waƙa, kamar haka.

Sharii'aa koo/ inaa tat ta/ sa koowaa,

Ta shuudce yaa/ ki yaa soo koo/ wance naa.

A wannan baiti na waƙa,yana da karin 'Hajaz ne wanda kafa ta biyu **Mafaa'iilun** (v ---) take maimaita kanta ta samar da shi. Idan an dubi layi na farko na baiti za a ga babu gabar karshe, sai ta koma(v --) har ma a layi na biyu na baitin, illar Hazfi ta shige ta, inda ta share gabar karshe, ta layin waƙar. Sai ta canza kafar ta tashi gada **Mafaa'iilun** (v ---) ta koma **Fa'iilun** (v --) sakamakon illar Hazfi da ta share gabar karshe.

A wani misalin waƙar ga yadda illar ta fito a cikin baiti kamar haka:

Mutaance gaa/ dokaa taanaa/ kai kuurecwaa,

Ga waayee zaa/ mu kookaa mai/ iyaawa.

Idan aka nazarci wannan baiti da kyau, za a fahimci layi na biyu na wakar babu gabar karshe, wanda ke nuni da an samu sakiya ta Hazfi, a cikinta inda ta shafe gabar ta karshe. Don karin bayani a nemi (Dunfawa, 2002).

Illa Mai Ragi ta Kadafi

Wannan illar ko sakiya tana samuwa idan sauyin “Asbi” (mai haɗe, gajerar gaba ta 3 da ta 4 a kafa ta 3) wato, kafa ta uku ita ce ‘**Mafaa’alatun** (v – vv –), sai kuma ya haɗu da illar “Hazfi” (mai shafe doguwar gaba ta karshe a cikin kafa wanda yake shiga kafafu tara da cikin goma) duk a cikin kafa ɗaya a lokaci ɗaya.

Misali, **Mafaa’alatun** (v – v v –) sai ta koma **Mafaa’ii** (v – –). Ga misali a cikin baitin waka kamar haka:

Mu goode Uban/gijinmu da yay/ yi koowaa,

Da yaa aikoo/ fiyayyen An/nabaawaa.

Baitin da ke sama yana bisa karin “Wafir” ne, wanda kafa ta uku **Mafaa’alatun** (v – v v –) ke maimaita kanta ta samar da shi. Amma idan aka lura sai a ga gaba ta karshe ta koma **Mafaa’ii** (v – –) a maimakon **Mafaa’alatun** (v – v v –).

Misali (v – v v v –) sai sauyin “Asbi” ya shiga ya haɗe gajerun gabobin biyu, wato gaba ta 3 da ta 4, sai tsarin ta ya koma (v – – –) sai kuma illar “Hazfi” ta zo, ita kuma ta shafe doguwar gabar karshe, sai tsarin ya koma (v - -). Wato dai, **Mafaa’alatun** (v – v v –) sai ta koma (v – – –) sannan (v – –) abin da ke nan ya faru ga wannan baitin waka da aka bayar da misalin sa, abin zai fi fitowa sosai idan aka samar da bayanin sauyi wato Zihafi, wanda mai aiki kan sauyi ko zihafi zai warware mana zare da abawa a kai.

Illa Mai Ragi Ta Kafa’i

Ita illar “Kafa’i” kamar yadda Dunfawa, (2002), ya nuna, tana shiga kafa ne wadda karshenta ya kare da gajerar gaba da doguwa, kamar haka (v –) inda take gunce doguwar gabar ta karshe ta mai da ta gajera, sai karshen gabar ya koma da gajerun gabobi kamar haka: (v v) sannan sai ta sake haɗe gajerun gabobin na karshe, ta mai da su doguwa ɗaya. Da zaran an ga haka, a cikin layi na baitocin waka, to, an samu sakiya ta kafa’i.

Akwai kafafi guda biyar daga cikin goma da aruli ya kunsu, waɗanda suke karewa da gajera da doguwar gaba a karshen su, su ne kamar haka:

Mafaa’alatun	V – V V –	sai ta koma	v – v v v	sannan	v – v –
Faa’ilun	– V –	ta koma	– v v	sannan	– –
Mustaf’ilun	– – V –	ta koma	– v v	sannan	– –
Mutafaa’ilun	V V – V –	ta koma	v v – v v	sannan	v v – –
Mustaf’ilun	– – V –	ta koma	– – v v	sannan	– – –

Ga yadda misali yake a cikin layi na baitin waka, kamar haka:

Yaa mai ribau/ccewar zukaa/taa ‘yan Adam

Naa zoo inaa/kaamun kafaa/wajjenkii.

Idan muka tsaya muka dubi wannan baiti, za a ga an yi amfani da kafar **Mustaf'ilun** (– v –), kafa ta shida, wadda take maimaita kanta ta samar da karin 'Rajaz'. A layin farko na baitin, gaɓoɓin waƙar sun fita dai-dai, amma a layi na biyu na baitin, za a ga, gaɓoɓi huɗu da ke samar da **Mustaf'ilun** (– v –) ta mai-maita sau biyu, amma a ta gaba, sai aka ga dogayen gaɓoɓi uku (– – –) maimaikon biyu da gajera da doguwa, saboda kada'i, ya cinye dogowar gabar ya mai da ta gajera (ki) sai kuma ya haɗe su ya maida su (kii) wato, gajerun sun koma doguwa ke nan. Wato dai, (– v –) ta koma (– v v) sannan (– – –) layin waƙar (waj-jen- ki – i – – v v) = (waj- jen- kii – – –).

A nan, an nuna sakiya ko illa ta kada'i ta shiga kafa ta shida ke nan, kuma duk da haka, ta kan kasance a sauran kafafu huɗun. Ita dai, wannan illa ko sakiya ta kada'i, a cikin kafafu biyar kawai ta ke shiga daga cikin kafafu goma da aruli ya kunsu. Kuma duk karuruwa da waɗannan kafafi ke samarwa za su iya gamuwa da wannan illa ko sakiya.

Illa Mai Ragi Ta Batari

Batari na daga cikin illar kari da ake da su. "Batari" illa ce wadda ke haɗa "Hazfi" (mai shafe doguwar gaba ta karshe a cikin kafa wanda ya ke shiga kafafu tara daga cikin goma) da "Kada'i" (mai mayar da doguwar gaba ta karshe kafa ta koma gajera tare da haɗe, gajerar gabar da ta gabace ta) a cikin kafa ɗaya a lokaci ɗaya. An fi samun wannan illa a kafa ta bakwai **Faa'ilaatun** (– v – –). Misali, **Faa'ilaatun** (– v – –) sai 'Hazfi' ya shigo ya shafe doguwar gaba ta karshe, sai ta koma **Faa'ilun** (– V –). Daga baya sai 'Kada'i' ya zo ya mayar da doguwar gabar da ta rage ta karshe ta koma gajera **Faa'ilu** (– v v). Sannan sai ya haɗe gajerun gaɓoɓin biyu su zama doguwa ɗaya, sai ta koma **Mustaf** (– –). Ga misali cikin wannan baitin waƙa :

*Baa ni taashi / inda nis/ san/ girmaa
Sai fa in suu/ sunka saa min / kaimii.*

Wannan baitin waƙa yana bisa karin 'Hafif' ne, wanda kafa ta **Faa'ilaatun** (– V –) ke maimaita kanta don samar da shi, wadda ke da turke a tsakiya da a bambanta ta da **Faa'ilaatun** (– V – –) ta huɗu mai turke a farko. Karin bayani a duba (Dunfawa, 2002).

Illa Mai Ragi ta Kashfi

Kashfi, na ɗaya daga cikin illar mai ragi wadda ke shiga tsakanin kafa, ta share wata gaba, wato dai, aikin kashfi yana gudana ne, a kan kafa ta tara **Maf'uulaatu** (– – – v) idan ta shiga wannan kafa, sai ta cire gajerar gaba ta karshe, sai ya koma **Maf'uulaa** wato, (– – –). Ga yadda abin ya ke kasancewa a cikin waƙa kamar haka:

*Mai tuukaa mo/ tar saiyya zo/ dudduukee,
Doomin kaafa/ fun naasaa sun/ mummurɗee.*

Wannan illa ta kashfi, ta fito a cikin wannan baiti tun a layi na farko, inda ta cire gabar karshe karama ta layin, haka kuma ta yi wa layi na biyu na baitin, duk kuwa da cewa baitin waƙar mai kwar biyu.

Illar Kari ACikin Aruli

Wannan shi ne kashi na biyu na illa ko kuma sakiya kamar yadda Dunfawa, (2002) ya ambata, ita wanna illar ta kari, tana kara wata gaba a cikin kafa, hakan kuma na canza kafar, wani lokacin ta kan tashi daga wata ta koma wata kafar daban. Wannan nau'in illa ta kasu kashi biyu, kamar haka:

1. Tarfili
2. Tazyili

Illar Kari Ta Tarfilu Cikin Aruli

Tarfilu nau'in illa ne, ta kari da ke kara wa kafa gaba daya ko biyu a ciki, wadda ke haddasa sauyawar ta. Wato dai, yana kara doguwar gaba a karshen kafa, kamar haka a cikin wannan baiti na waƙa.

An sanya har/ sheccikin baa/kii,

Iikon tabaa/raaka mai tsar/kii.

Wannan baiti yana kan karin Mujtaƙa wanda kafafun **Mustaf'ilun** (– – v –) da **Faa'ilaatun** (– V – –) ke samar wa, za a ga a layin farko na baiti an samu karin gaba a karshe, inda maimaikon **Faa'ilaatun** (– V – –) sai ta koma (– V – – –) haka ma ya afku a layi na biyu na baiti.

Illar Kari Ta Tazyili Cikin Aruli

Tazyili, ita ma tana daga cikin nau'in illa mai kari, inda take shigacikin kafa ta tara **Maf'uulaatu** (– – – v). Sannan idan ta shiga, sai ta kara wa gajerar gaƙar ta karshe wata gajerar gaba, ta koma (– – – v) sai ta kuma haƙe su wuri ɗaya ta koma (– – –). Wato, ta mai da su doguwa.

Ga misali a cikin wannan baitin waƙa.

Areewa ban da/ an cuuce mu/u,

Daayanzuu duu/niiyaa taa sanmu/u.

A nan kafar **Maf'uulaatu** (– – – v) wadda ta kasance kafa ta uku, wadda ke maimaita kanta ta samar da karin Wafir, ita ce a kan wannan baiti. Inda a layi na farko aka samu illar kari ta tazyili, inda aka samu karin gajerar gaba, wadda kuma suka haƙe suka zama doguwa ɗaya.

Kammalawa

Illa ko sakiya abu ce da ke jagoranci ga mai nazari ya lalubo lungu da saƙo da ta ke wanzuwa a cikin baiti na waƙa, wanda ke samuwa daga haɗuwar gaƙobi uku ko fiye, da suke gina kafafu, da ke haɗuwa su samar da kari. Walau ta hanyar maimaici ko gwamawa ko kuma kafa ta maimaita kanta sannan ta haɗu da wata su samar da kari.

Kamar dai, yadda ake yanka baiti don fitar da illa ko sakiya, ta hanyar sauraron waƙa daga wanda ya rera ta ko kuma a ɗakin na'ura mai kƙaƙwalwa

(language laboratory) ko a rubuta a takarda a daddatsa, kamar yadda wannan takarda ta yi wajen yanka baitocin waƙoƙin da aka kafa misalai da su.

Wannan takarda ta yi bayani dalla-dalla kan abin da ya shafi illa ko sakiya, ko kuma a kira shi da naƙasu da ke faruwa a cikin layukan baitocin waƙa, kamar yadda aka gani tun daga naƙasun da ake samu da ya kasu kashi biyu ; na rafi da na kari.

Haka ma, takardar ta gano naƙasu na Hazfi na shiga cikin kafafu tara daga cikin goma da ake da su. Wato dai, a cikin gaƙar **Maf'uulatu** kawai ke bai shiga. Hakan ya nuna mafi rinjayen karuruwan da kafafu ke samarwa ana iya samun naƙasu a cikin misalan waƙoƙin da aka safa a cikin baiti.

Tuntuɓe karin gushi, takardar ta gano naƙasu ba ruwanshi da turke, zai iya shiga kowace kafa a gaƙarta ta karshe, walau doguwa ko gajera, ya iya shiga cikin a samar da naƙasu a wurin inda waƙar Hausa ce.

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